

THE ROLE OF GUAR GUM IN GUT AND OTHER DISORDERS**Dr. Priyanka Anjinappa^{1*}, Shilpa M.², Samudha C. N.², Kavya G.³**

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ABSTRACT

The powdered endosperm of the seeds of the leguminous crop *Cyamopsis tetragonolobus* is known as guar gum. Galactomannan, a polymer of d-galactose and d-mannose, is a complex polysaccharide found in the endosperm. When this hydroxyl group-rich polymer is introduced to water, hydrogen bonds are formed, giving the mixture a noticeable increase in viscosity and thickness. It is used in many different industries because of its thickening, emulsifying, binding, and gelling qualities; rapid solubility in cold water; broad pH stability; film-forming capacity; and biodegradability. It is widely used in the pharmaceutical, cosmetic, food, textile, paper, explosives, and toiletry industries, among other sectors. It is employed in pharmaceuticals as a controlled-release carrier, suspending, thickening, stabilizing, and as a tablet binder and disintegrant. Guar gum is a hydrocolloidal polysaccharide that

is made up of the sugars mannose and galactose in a molecular ratio of 1:1.4-1:2. In medicine, it is used as a bulk-forming laxative, hypoglycemic, hypolipidemic, antibacterial, anti-proliferative, and appetite suppressant, and in Crohn's disease and colitis, among other conditions. The current analysis provides detailed information on the variety of medicinal,

chemical, pharmacological, and industrial applications of guar gum. Modified guar gum is widely used in pharmaceutical applications due to its viscosity-enhancing properties.

KEYWORDS: Guar gum, Gut health, gastrointestinal disorders, Anti-inflammatory, wound healing.

INTRODUCTION

In blood lipid levels

The particular signs of dyslipidemia were associated with a drop in HDL-C and an increase in TC, LDL-C, and TG. In numerous countries, the degree of changes in blood lipid is rated as an indicator for monitoring individual blood lipid health status.^[1] Lipid levels are a diagnostic indicator for many chronic diseases such as diabetes and CVD.^[2] Age, gender, diet, and lifestyle can all have an impact on blood lipid levels.^[3]

Role of guar gum

Because of its solubility, high viscosity, and fermentability, soluble fiber is thought to help decrease blood lipid levels.^[4] Guar gum is often used as a food additive to emulsify, thicken, and solidify processed foods, such as baked goods, breakfast cereals, and dairy products, for its rich dietary fiber and outstanding viscosity.^[5] Guar gum intervention in the diet for 48 weeks dramatically decreased TC and LDL-C concentrations in adults with diabetes, according to the study.^[6] However, a 6-month RCT showed that, in addition to lowering LDL-C levels in men, guar gum did not alter lipid profiles in diabetic patients compared to the controls.^[7]

In body weight reduction

Numerous types of fiber supplements have been introduced during the last decade, claiming special effects on weight reduction. In some reports, the water-soluble and viscous fiber guar gum has been shown to reduce body weight^[8, 9] whereas in a meta-analysis.^[10] Guar gum was not found to be effective in reducing body weight. The water-soluble and highly viscous fiber glucomannan has been reported to reduce the body weight in some studies.^[11,12] Alginate is a viscous fiber that reduces cholesterol secretion and has been proposed as a dietary fiber to reduce body weight.^[13] Furthermore, fiber's ability to reduce weight has also been connected to its viscosity. The delayed absorption of the macronutrients is thought to be caused by the viscosity of the dietary component.^[14] And increased satiety.^[15,16] Fiber-rich foods have been linked to a decreased risk of diabetes and cardiovascular disease.^[17-23] Fiber's ability to

decrease cholesterol has received the most attention.^[18,24,25] In short-term studies, fiber supplements have been demonstrated to cause weight loss.^[8,12] A low-calorie diet, a fiber supplement, and little exercise seem to be a promising strategy for losing weight.^[26]

Constipation in dialysis patients

Constipation is one of the most frequently reported gastrointestinal complaints in patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) undergoing dialysis.

Epidemiology of Constipation in Dialysis: Studies consistently report a high prevalence of constipation in both hemodialysis and peritoneal dialysis patients. Reduced fiber intake and altered gut microbiota are strongly associated with symptom severity. Constipation and alterations in gut bacterial flora are common in dialysis patients. Patients suffering from renal failure have elevated levels of indoxylsulfuric acid (IS), which increases as glomerular filtration falls. Increased indole as a result of changed gut flora also contributes to elevated IS.^[27]

Mechanism of Action of Guar Gum in Constipation of dialysis patients: Guar gum absorbs water, increases stool bulk, and undergoes fermentation to produce short-chain fatty acids that enhance colonic motility and gut health. One of the earliest signs of a fiber-deficient condition was constipation. We looked at whether giving dialysis patients partly hydrolyzed guar gum (PHGG) will enhance their nutritional status and alleviate constipation while lowering IS levels. For six weeks, 35 patients on maintenance dialysis consumed 10 g of PHGG daily. A modified Constipation Assessment Scale-Long Term (Japanese version) was used to rate defecation both before and after PHGG ingestion. The Geriatric Nutritional Risk Index (GNRI) was used to assess nutritional status both before and after PHGG consumption. For comparison with eight patients who were not on PHGG, IS (indoxylsulphuric acid) was assessed in eight patients who were taking PHGG orally for 24 weeks. Constipation scores dropped from 7.9 to 5.0 ($p < .01$), and GNRI rose from 95.0 ± 5.0 to 95.9 ± 5.7 ($p < .05$), indicating improved nutritional status and a reduction in constipation. To determine the extent of IS alteration, the ratio of IS after to that before PHGG ingestion was computed. In patients not on PHGG, the ratio was 1.2 ± 0.3 , meaning that IS increased, but in patients on PHGG, it was considerably lower (0.8 ± 0.3 , $p < .05$). According to our findings, PHGG ingestion improves nutritional status, lessens constipation, and lowers indoxylsulphuric acid (IS) in dialysis patients.^[27]

In constipation

EPIDEMIOLOGY

One of the earliest signs of a fiber-deficient condition was constipation. Fecal impaction, incontinence, and delirium can result from persistent constipation (received December 21, 2021). It can result in a rise in hospital admissions and a reduction in everyday activities.^[28,29]

Role of guar gum: It has been demonstrated that dietary fiber increases intestinal motility and improves fecal size and consistency. People who consume a high-protein diet often have fecal weights of about 100 g per day, whereas those who consume a high-carbohydrate and high-fiber diet typically have fecal weights of about 300 g per day.^[30] It has been demonstrated that various dietary fiber supplements can improve stool frequency and reduce the need for laxatives in LTCF residents.^[31, 32] Fecal impaction, incontinence, and delirium can result from persistent constipation (received December 21, 2021). It can result in a rise in hospital admissions and a reduction in everyday activities.^[28,29] 150 g of feces per day has been recommended as a therapeutic target for constipation alleviation.^[33] Fiber's impact on fecal bulk is thought to be linked to both bacterial growth stimulation and water-holding capacity.^[34] Guar gum, a water-soluble, viscous, gelling polysaccharide present in the seeds of *Cyamopsis tetragonolobus*, is the source of partially hydrolyzed guar gum (PHGG), a water-soluble, non-viscous, non-gelling vegetable dietary fiber.^[35,36] It has been demonstrated that PHGG is useful in reducing irritable bowel syndrome symptoms and enhancing quality of life.^[37] A daily use of 20 g of guar gum has been shown to raise the fecal weight of healthy volunteers by 20%.^[38] It speeds up the colon's transit time in people who have persistent constipation.^[39] However, a daily consumption of 11.4 g of guar gum did not raise fecal weight in another trial.^[40] Iron and other micronutrient absorption is unaffected by PHGG, which is safe and well-tolerated.^[41,42] The partially hydrolyzed guar gum (PHGG) utilized in our investigation had a substantially lower molecular weight and viscosity than intact guar gum, and giving 36 g of PHGG daily to healthy participants increased fecal volume by up to 42%.^[43] The effects of water-soluble dietary fiber on constipated people's fecal volume, pH, moisture, and bacteria have not been extensively studied so far. PHGG has a lesser risk of the abovementioned problems and is better tolerated. The microbiota benefits from dietary fiber supplementation through PHGG. We were unable to locate any randomized studies evaluating PHGG's efficacy in LTCF residents during the literature review. This study evaluates how well it helps LTCF residents with constipation and lowers their use of laxatives.

In childhood constipation

The prevalence of constipation in children has been observed to range from 0.8 to 28%. After receiving effective treatment for constipation, about half of the children relapse. Toilet training, a high-fiber diet, and long-term oral laxatives are now recommended treatments for functional constipation.^[44] There is not enough information in the literature to offer recommendations based on evidence regarding the most efficient fiber sources.^[45] Role of guar gum: Due to its low viscosity and full fermentation in the colon, partially hydrolyzed guar gum (PHGG) is one of the most promising sources of fiber.^[46] While lactulose is a synthetic sugar osmotic laxative, guar gum is a natural soluble dietary fiber that acts as a prebiotic. PHGG and lactulose are both effective treatments for constipation, but they differ significantly in their mechanism, side effect profiles, and additional health benefits.

Properties	PHGG	Lactulose
Sources and Types	*Produced through the enzymatic hydrolysis of raw guar gum. *Natural soluble fiber and act as a prebiotic	*It is a synthetic disaccharide sugar produced from lactulose (milk sugar) *Synthetic osmotic laxatives
Mainly used	Constipation and IBS	Constipation
Side effects	Rarely leads to low gas, bloating	Commonly; Gas, bloating, cramps
Taste	Generally neutral	Very sweet
GIT Health	Increases beneficial bacteria (prebiotic)	Modifies flora, but primarily draws water
Others	Lowers cholesterol, aids weight management	None (beyond bowel function)

Fig 1: Comparative studies between PHGG and Lactulose.

As far as we know from the English literature, there has been no study that investigated the use of PHGG in childhood constipation. The purpose of our study was to evaluate the therapeutic role of PHGG in children with chronic constipation and to compare its effects with lactulose treatment.

In irritable bowel syndrome (IBS)

"A group of functional bowel disorders in which abdominal discomfort or pain is associated with defecation or a change in bowel habit, and with features of disordered defecation" is the meaning of irritable bowel syndrome (IBS).^[47] Irritable bowel syndrome is frequently marked by bloating, lower abdominal pain, changed bowel habits, excessive flatulence, and/or distention of the abdomen, endured for a long time.^[48] Many physicians believe that the definition of IBS is restrictive in clinical practice and should include individuals without

discomfort, pending the existence of other criteria, even if it is based on the findings of a working team of specialists. Practically speaking, IBS is diagnosed based on these criteria and in the absence of warning signs including fever, bleeding, and weight loss.^[49] These symptoms have a detrimental impact on a person's mental health and quality of life (QOL), as seen by increased rates of dysphoria, negative body image, food avoidance, health concerns, activity disruption, and problems with social and romantic relationships.^[50] A considerable workload within both primary and secondary care is created from IBS patients, with roughly 3.6 million physician office visits a year and more than \$30 billion in IBS-related healthcare costs globally.^[51,54] IBS is divided into a number of subgroups, such as IBS with mixed bowel habits, IBS with constipation (IBS-C), and IBS with diarrhea (IBS-D).^[48] Two further FBDs that are categorized using the Rome criteria are functional diarrhea (FD) and functional constipation (FC).^[55] Inadequate defecation, hard or infrequent stool transit, and/or the feeling of incomplete stool evacuation without an underlying biological cause are the hallmarks of FC.^[56,57] Functional diarrhea, which affects more than 25% of stools, is characterized by loose or watery stools without prominent bloating or abdominal pain.^[58]

Role of guar gum in IBS, FC and FD: The fact that soluble fiber absorbs water and creates a gel after digestion, which is said to make the stool softer and easier to pass.^[59,60] The impact of insoluble fiber on the consistency and transit time of feces is used.^[59] Guar fiber, also known as partially hydrolyzed guar gum, is a water-soluble polysaccharide derived from the seeds of the guar plant, which is native to India and Pakistan.^[61] According to earlier research, guar fiber is useful for softening, improving fecal output, and increasing bulking capacity (fecal excretory feeling, frequency of defecation, and fecal weight).^[62,63] Guar fiber is thought to have the capacity to protect and improve digestive health both on its own and in a symbiotic combination with probiotics.^[64] Additionally guar fiber has shown promise as a soluble fiber for the management and prevention of FC, FD, and IBS.^[64,65] The guar fiber dosage required to produce statistically meaningful changes is not well-supported by these reviews. Furthermore, the prospective use of guar fiber for the treatment of IBS, FC, and FD has not been investigated in any clinical recommendations. Because the symptoms and diagnostic criteria for IBS, FC, and FD are similar, all three disorders have been chosen for inclusion. This is because guar fiber uses the same mechanism to alleviate these symptoms.^[66,67] **Guar gum clinical overview:** It is challenging to add sufficient amounts of guar gum to foods or enteral solutions because of its high viscosity. Guar gum undergoes controlled partial enzymatic hydrolysis to yield PHGG. Because of its reduced molecular

weight (20,000 Da), PHGG is less viscous than the original guar gum and does not gel. Due to these unique qualities and the fact that it still has the advantages of guar gum.^[68] When assessing medications or dietary supplements, safety is the most important factor. Up to 10% of PHGG in the diet did not cause any harm in lab animals.^[69] Additionally assessed were the effects of PHGG on fecal production in both constipated patients and healthy volunteers. In healthy volunteers, PHGG supplementation as a beverage at a dosage of 36 g/d increased fecal bulk and solids by 38.4% and 37.3%, respectively.^[70] In healthy individuals, two distinct PHGG dosages (5 versus 15 g/d) had comparable outcomes, meaning that both PHGG programs improved fecal consistency and increased the frequency of defecation.^[71] Patients with sepsis who received both PHGG and regular enteral nutrition experienced fewer days of diarrhea than those who received enteral feeding alone in a double-blind, randomized experiment.^[72] These investigations served as the foundation for a multicenter, randomized, open study that examined the effects of wheat bran supplementation against PHGG in a large number of IBS patients, including subgroups with constipation and diarrhea.^[73] The beneficial benefits of PHGG on IBS were more frequently noted at the conclusion of treatment (3 months) than at the 6-month follow-up, according to the study that actually followed patients.^[74] This emphasizes even more how important it is for patients with conditions like IBS, which are marked by spontaneous fluctuations in symptoms, to have adequate follow-up evaluations.^[75,76]

Role of guar gum and wheat bran in IBS: Dietary fiber, a heterogeneous group of complex carbohydrates that are resistant to breakdown by human digestive enzymes, is one of the most often utilized therapeutic strategies for IBS. Dietary fiber is believed to provide nondigestible bulk, retain water, and act as a substrate for microbial development in the colon, all of which increase stool weight and shorten colon transit time.^[77] Despite being widely used in the clinical treatment of IBS, fiber supplementation may cause two issues. First, bloating may make high-fiber diets intolerable for certain individuals, who may even believe that their IBS symptoms are getting worse.^[78,79] It's unclear why bran exacerbates IBS symptoms, but IBS sufferers may have a lower pain threshold and be more susceptible to intestinal gas production from bacterial fermentation of the fiber and the ensuing intraluminal distension.^[80] However, as far as we are aware, no controlled study has looked into how PHGG affects IBS patients. Comparing the advantages of PHGG with the high-fiber diet frequently employed in the clinical care of IBS was the goal of this study. Regrettably, IBS does not have a conventional therapy. One of the main, difficult objectives of treating IBS patients is to

reduce their symptoms. However, rational management of this prevalent disorder is challenging, in part because we still lack objective criteria for making a definitive diagnosis, its pathogenesis is unknown, and as a result, there are no specific, effective therapies.^[81] Actually, a complex interplay of nutritional, behavioral, social, functional, and biological variables may be the cause of IBS symptoms. IBS can be treated with a variety of pharmacological treatments, but despite their widespread usage, it has been challenging to prove their effectiveness in controlled clinical studies, in part due to the high placebo response rates (up to 70%) seen in IBS trials.^[82] It is also challenging to choose acceptable endpoints that show changes in the breadth of symptoms because there aren't any biological indicators for IBS.^[83]

Properties	Wheat bran	PHGG
Fiber type	Insoluble fiber	Soluble fiber
Tolerability	Not tolerable	Better tolerated
Primary IBS benefit habits	Constipation relief	Pain, bloating and bowel
Gas/Bloating	Often increases	Significantly reduces
Success rate	40%	60%
Compliance	Lower	Higher

Fig. 2: Comparative study of wheat bran and PHGG.

While both fibers can theoretically improve core IBS symptoms, PHGG is significantly superior to wheat bran due to its patient tolerability and broader effectiveness.

In pediatric functional abdominal pain

Functional gastrointestinal disorders (FGIDs) are characterized as a variable collection of chronic or recurrent gastrointestinal (GI) symptoms; they are age dependent and not explained by structural or biochemical abnormalities.^[84] The most prevalent ailment among FGIDs is chronic abdominal pain (CAP). It is normally functioning without objective indication of an underlying biological disease.^[85] Several studies revealed that 13% of middle-school pupils and 17% of high school students have weekly experience of stomach pain.^[86,87]

Role of guar gum: The positive effects of water-soluble dietary fibers have garnered attention as supplemental therapy in FGIDs, especially in FAP and IBS, for their capacity to modify bowel pattern, speed oral-to-anal transit and decrease intracolonic pressure and alleviate pain.^[88,89] Shown, in an adult open trial, that PHGG supplementation is followed by a

decrease of IBS symptoms, such as abdominal pain and bowel habit.^[90] Supplementation can alleviate symptoms in children with FAP, according to a small, prospective, randomized study. Despite this, there have been no recently available published randomized controlled trials (RCTs) to support the use of fiber in the treatment of CAP in a pediatric population. The purpose of this study was to evaluate how the PHGG food supplement affected the symptoms of IBS and CAP in the pediatric population.

In cancer

Colitis-associated colorectal cancer (CAC) is characterized as a kind of CRC that is typically encountered in patients with inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). Prolonged colonic inflammation considerably raises the risk of CAC compared to healthy persons.^[91,92]

As the third most common cause of cancer-related mortality in the US, colorectal cancer (CRC) presents a serious public health concern.^[93] Factors leading to CRC include aging, genetic predisposition, environmental influences, and chronic intestinal inflammation.^[94]

Role of Guar gum: DFs (Dietary fibres) are complex carbohydrates that are edible yet difficult for humans to digest. DFs are widely divided into insoluble and soluble based on their solubility in water. In both humans and mice, insoluble fibers such as cellulose are often resistant to fermentation by gut microbes. They provide a number of health advantages, including increased stool size and a laxative impact, despite having little bacterial degradation.^[95] ^bOne possible way to fulfill their daily requirement is to add isolated dietary fibers (DFs) to processed foods. This strategy, in fact, is touted as having greater nutritional value for certain meals and assisting in fulfilling fiber requirements. Both human and mouse gut flora may easily ferment soluble DFs like inulin and partially hydrolyzed guar gum (PHGG). Additionally, the host's metabolic and gastrointestinal (GI) health can benefit greatly from these soluble DFs.^[96] Improvements in intestinal health indices, such as increased gut barrier function.^[97] Lowered levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines.^[98] Upon consuming these soluble DFs, primarily stemmed from interventional studies conducted in cohorts of healthy rodents and human populations. Whether DF supplementation produces similar effects during continuous intestinal inflammation remains mostly unknown and has begun to be unraveled recently. These recent investigations have generated conflicting conclusions regarding the influence of refined DFs on intestinal health. A subset of this research reveals positive benefits on intestinal inflammation.^[99,102] In this study, we assessed PHGG, a soluble DF commonly used in the food sector as a food thickener and

emulsifier,^[103] and accessible as a supplement on measures of cell survival and proliferation as well as colonic inflammation. Furthermore, we used a model of colon cancer linked to colitis to assess the impact of PHGG on colon carcinogenesis.^[104]

In diabetes

The metabolic syndrome (MetS), which refers to a cluster of risk factors comprising central obesity, low serum HDL-cholesterol and elevated serum TAG, blood pressure and blood glucose.^[105] Raises the risk of all-cause mortality and doubles the risk of cardiovascular events^[106] 85% of people with type 2 diabetes have the MetS.^[107]

Role of guar gum: Dietary intervention is crucial for managing the components of MetS.^[108] On the other hand, nothing is known about how fiber consumption affects people with diabetes and the MetS. We recently showed that the existence of the MetS was positively correlated with low total fiber content in individuals with type 2 diabetes, which is linked to consumption of foods with a high dietary glycemic index.^[109] The controlled partial enzymatic hydrolysis of guar gum (GG) yields partially hydrolyzed guar gum (PHGG), a naturally occurring water-soluble dietary fiber that is tasteless and simple to incorporate into the diet.^[110,111] Guar gum has a proven ability to decrease cholesterol in individuals with high cholesterol who are not diabetics.^[112,115] As well as in non-insulin-dependent diabetic patients.^[116,118] Additionally, among individuals with type 2 diabetes, the existence of the MetS was adversely correlated with the consumption of soluble fibers, particularly from whole-grain meals and fruits.^[119] The contentious results on glucose metabolism in non-insulin-dependent diabetes can be explained, at least in part, by the interference of guar gum in the absorption of some,^[120] but not all,^[121] oral antidiabetic medicines in these individuals. Whether dietary guar gum can improve glycemic control and the serum lipid and lipoprotein profiles in hyperlipidemic insulin dependent diabetic patients treated with insulin injections is unclear. Guar gum decreased the postprandial rise in plasma glucose following a test meal in well-controlled, normolipidemic individuals receiving continuous subcutaneous insulin infusion, whereas hemoglobin (Hb) A1 concentration remained unchanged during the course of long-term treatment.^[122] When a diet rich in natural fiber was supplemented with guar^[123] or with doses not feasible for nutritional usage.^[124] Patients with poorly managed insulin-dependent diabetes showed a drop in HbA1. We are not aware of any research examining the influence of dietary guar on glycemic control and serum lipid or lipoprotein concentrations in insulin-dependent diabetic patients treated with insulin injections and the standard diabetic

diet. Because patients with insulin-dependent diabetes also have a higher prevalence of coronary heart disease.^[125] Other research have not validated these positive effects of GG both in glucose^[126,128] and cholesterol levels.^[152] It is crucial to know whether guar gum could be used as a cholesterol-lowering medication in these patients also. And it is currently unknown how GG may affect MetS components in individuals with type 2 diabetes.

Wound healing property of guar gum

Hydrogel composites have uses in wound care that go beyond their antibacterial properties; they promote the formation of new blood vessels and increase fibroblast activity, which turns the inflammatory stage into a proliferative healing phase. These composites also target gene expression, which encourages tissue remodeling and guarantees strong wound recovery.^[130]

Anti-inflammatory property of guar gum

According to recent studies, oligosaccharides contribute to the therapeutic anti-inflammatory effects shown in the management of inflammatory bowel disease. Other polysaccharides, however, are being investigated for a variety of uses. Simple sugars are produced when guar gum is hydrolyzed. Although guar gum has several medical uses, its possible anti-inflammatory properties in the treatment of inflammatory bowel disease are still unknown. Guar gum used orally acts as a binder, facilitates breakdown, and lessens irritation of the mucosa. It is therefore a potentially effective therapy for inflammatory bowel disease.^[131]

CONCLUSION

A soluble galactomannan fiber obtained from *Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*, guar gum exhibits a wide range of therapeutic promise for inflammatory, gastrointestinal, and metabolic disorders. Guar gum has demonstrated steady lipid-reduction benefits in relation to cardiovascular health, especially in lowering levels of total and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol. It improves blood lipid profiles and may lower the overall risk of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease by increasing bile acid excretion and encouraging hepatic cholesterol utilization. Additionally, guar gum is important for intestinal health. It works well for chronic constipation because of its bulking and stool-softening qualities, which also increase bowel frequency and consistency. When administered properly, guar gum provides a non-systemic, fiber-based strategy for enhancing bowel motility in dialysis patients, who frequently suffer from constipation as a result of fluid limitations and drug use, without negatively impacting renal function. In a similar vein, guar gum offers a mild, well-tolerated substitute for stimulant laxatives in cases of infantile constipation, assisting in the

restoration of normal bowel patterns and enhancing quality of life. By regulating bowel movements and promoting a healthy gut microbiota through fermentation into short-chain fatty acids, guar gum helps alleviate symptoms of functional gastrointestinal diseases including irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) and pediatric functional abdominal pain. These metabolites may lessen intestinal inflammation and visceral hypersensitivity, which would improve discomfort in the abdomen. Guar gum has strong anti-diabetic effects from a metabolic standpoint. It efficiently reduces insulin demand and blunts postprandial glucose rises by delaying stomach emptying and lowering glucose absorption rates. Long-term supplementation may enhance insulin sensitivity and glycemic control, bolstering dietary approaches for the management of type 2 diabetes. Guar gum's promise in tissue healing and cancer is further highlighted by new research. Guar gum may lower the risk of colorectal cancer by increasing fecal volume, decreasing intestinal transit time, and producing healthy short-chain fatty acids like butyrate. It is also appropriate for biomedical uses in wound healing, where it promotes moist wound conditions, cellular proliferation, and tissue regeneration due to its biocompatible, gel-forming qualities. Additionally, guar gum has anti-inflammatory properties that are mediated via decreased systemic inflammatory indicators, enhanced intestinal barrier integrity, and modification of the gut microbiota. Its wider importance in avoiding chronic inflammatory and metabolic diseases is reinforced by these activities.

REFERENCES

1. Jacobson, T. A., Ito, M. K., Maki, K. C., Orringer, C. E., Bays, H. E., Jones, P. H., ... Brown, W. V. (2015). National lipid association recommendations for patient- centered management of dyslipidemia: Part 1–full report. *Journal of Clinical Lipidology*, 9(2): 129–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacl.2015.02.003>.
2. Ofori, E. K., Intiful, F. D., Asante, M., Asare, G. A., Adjei, P. K., Steele-Dadzie, R. K., ... Angmortherh, S. K. (2018). Prevalence of cardiovascular disease risk factors among students of a tertiary institution in Ghana. *Food Science & Nutrition*, 6(2): 381–387. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fsn3.565>.
3. Xi, Y., Niu, L., Cao, N., Bao, H., Xu, X., Zhu, H., Zhang, X. (2020). Prevalence of dyslipidemia and associated risk factors among adults aged ≥ 35 years in northern China: A cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health*, 20(1): 1068. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-09172-9>.

4. Surampudi, P., Enkhmaa, B., Anuurad, E., & Berglund, L. (2016). Lipid Lowering with Soluble Dietary Fiber. *Current Atherosclerosis Reports*, 18(12): 75. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11883-016-0624-z>.
5. Mortensen, A., Aguilar, F., Crebelli, R., Di Domenico, A., Frutos, M. J., Galtier, P., Dusemund, B. (2017). Re-evaluation of guar gum (E 412) as a food additive. *EFSA Journal*. European Food Safety Authority, 15(2): Article e04669. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2017.4669>.
6. Groop, P. H., Aro, A., Stenman, S., & Groop, L. (1993). Long-term effects of guar gum in subjects with non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 58(4): 513–518. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/58.4.513>.
7. McIvor, M. E., Cummings, C. C., Van Duyn, M. A., Leo, T. A., Margolis, S., Behall, K. M., ... Mendeloff, A. I. (1986). Long-term effects of guar gum on blood lipids. *Atherosclerosis*, 60(1): 7–13. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9150\(86\)90081-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9150(86)90081-x).
8. Uusitupa M, Tuomilehto J, Karttunen P, Wolf E: Long term effects of guar gum on metabolic control, serum cholesterol and blood pressure levels in type 2 (non-insulin-dependent) diabetic patients with high blood pressure. *Ann Clin Res.*, 1984; 16(Suppl.43): 126–31 11.
9. Krotkiewski M: Effect of guar gum on body-weight, hunger ratings and metabolism in obese subjects. *Br J Nutr.*, 1984; 52(1): 97–105.
10. Pittler MH, Ernst E: Guar gum for body weight reduction: meta-analysis of randomized trials. *Am J Med.*, 2001; 110(9): 724–30. Tuomilehto J, Voutilainen E, Huttunen J et al: Effect of guar gum on body weight and serum lipids in hypercholesterolemic females. *Acta Med Scand*, 1980; 208: 45–48.
11. Walsh DE, Yaghoubian V, Behforooz A: Effect of glucomannan on obese patients: a clinical study. *Int J Obes*, 1984; 8(4): 289–93.
12. Livieri C, Novazi F, Lorini R: The use of highly purified glucomannan based fibers in childhood obesity. *Pediatr Med Chir*, 1992; 14(2): 195–98.
13. Kimura Y, Watanabe K, Okuda H: Effects of soluble sodium alginate on cholesterol excretion and glucose tolerance in rats. *J Ethnopharmacol.*, 1996; 54(1): 47–54.
14. Schneeman BO: Dietary fiber and gastrointestinal function. *Nutr Rev.*, 1987; 45(5): 129–32 21.
15. Marciani L, Gowland PA, Fillery-Travis A et al: Assessment of antral grinding of a model solid meal with echo-planar imaging.: *Am J Physiol Gastrointest Liver Physiol.*, 2001; 280(5): G844–49 22.

16. Burton-Freeman B: Dietary fiber and energy regulation. *J Nutr.*, 2000; 130(Suppl. 2S): 272S–75S.
17. Ludwig-DS, Pereira-MA, Kroenke-CH et al: Dietary fiber, weight gain, and cardiovascular disease risk factors in young adults. *JAMA.*, 1999; 282(16): 1539–46.
18. Brown L, Rosner B, Willett WW, Sacks FM: Cholesterol-lowering effects of dietary fiber: a meta-analysis *Am J Clin Nutr.*, 1999; 69: 30–42.
19. Nelson-LH, Tucker-LA: Diet composition related to body fat in a multivariate study of 203 men. *J Am Diet Assoc.*, 1996; 96(8): 771–77.
20. Alexander H, Lockwood LP, Harris MA, Melby CL: Risk factors for cardiovascular disease and diabetes in two groups of Hispanic Americans with differing dietary habits. *J Am Coll Nutr.*, 1999; 18: 127–36.
21. Ludwig-DS, Pereira-MA, Kroenke-CH et al: Dietary fiber, weight gain, and cardiovascular disease risk factors in young adults. *JAMA.*, 1999; 282(16): 1539–46.
22. Liu-S, Stampfer-MJ, Hu-FB et al: Whole-grain consumption and risk of coronary heart disease: results from the Nurses' Health Study. *Am J Clin Nutr.*, 1999; 70(3): 412–1.
23. Bennett WG; Cerda JJ: Benefits of dietary fiber. Myth or medicine? *Postgrad Med*, 1996; 99(2): 153–56, 166–68, 171–72.
24. Zhou W, Chai H, Lin PH et al: Molecular mechanisms and clinical applications of ginseng root for cardiovascular disease. *Med Sci Monit.*, 2004; 10(8): 187–92.
25. Birketvedt GS, Travis A, Langbakk B, Florholmen R: Dietary Supplementation with Bean Extract Improves Lipid Profile in Overweight and Obese Subjects. *Nutrition*, 2002; 18: 1–6.
26. Joint FAO/WHO Expert Consultation: Carbohydrates in human nutrition. Geneva: Food and Agriculture Organization, World health Organization, 1998; (FAO Food and Nutrition Paper 66).
27. Hiroto Maeda, Tomoko Uemura, Makoto Nasu, Natsumi Iwata, Junko Yoshimura, Shoji Sakai Shimonoseki City Hospital, Yamaguchi, Japan
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.krcp.2012.04.470>.
28. Tariq SH, Morley JE, Prather CM. Health issues in the elderly: Fecal incontinence: Importance, clinical evaluation and treatment. *Am J Med.*, 2003; 115: 217-227, DOI: 10.1016/s0002-9343(03)00327-9.
29. Musa MK, Saga S, Blekken LE, Harris R, et al. The prevalence, incidence and correlates of fecal incontinence among older people residing in care homes: a systematic review.

- Journal of American Medical Directors Association, 2019; 20: 956-962, DOI: 10.1016/j.jamda., 2019.03; 033.
30. Rendtorff, R. C., and Kashgarian, M. (1967): Stool patterns of healthy adult males. *Dis., Colon Rectum.*, 10: 222-228.
 31. Bug S, Brinckman J, Cicconetti G, Valentine B. Efficacy of a herbal dietary supplement (Smooth Move) in the management of constipation in nursing home residents. *Journal of the American Medical Directors Association*, 2006; 7: 556-561, DOI: 10.1016/j.jamda.2006.06.001.
 32. Dahl WJ, Mendoza DR. Is fiber an effective strategy to improve laxation in long term care residents? *Canadian Journal of Dietetic Practice and Research*, 2018; 79: 35-41, DOI: 10.3148/cjdpr-2017-028.
 33. Spiller, G. A., Chernoff, M. C., Shipley, E. A., Beigler, M. A., and Briggs, G. M. (1977): Can fecal weight be used to establish a recommended intake of dietary fiber (plantix)?. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.*, 30: 659-661.
 34. Stephen, A. M., and Cummings, J. H. (1980): Mechanism of action of dietary fiber in the human colon. *Nature*, 284, 283-284.
 35. Giannini EG, Mansi C, Dulbecco P, et al. Role of partially hydrolyzed guar gum in the treatment of irritable bowel syndrome. *Nutrition*, 2006; 22: 334-342, DOI: 10.1016/j.nut.2005.10.003.
 36. Quaratone G. Role of PHGG as a dietary fiber: a review article. *Minerva Gastroenterol Dietol*, 2013; 59: 329-340, PMID: 24212352.
 37. Niv E, Halak A, Tiommny E, et al. Randomized clinical study: Partially hydrolyzed guar gum (PHGG) versus placebo in the treatment of patients with irritable bowel syndrome. *Nutrition & Metabolism*, 2016; 13: 10, DOI: 10.1186/s12986-016-0070-5
 38. Cummings, J. H., Southgate, D. A. T., Branchi, W., Houston H., Jenkins, D. J. A., and James, W. P. T. (1978): Colonic response to dietary fiber from carrot, cabbage, apple, bran, and guar gum. *Lancet*, 1, 5-8.
 39. Polymeros D, Beintaris I, Gaglia A, et al. Partially hydrolyzed guar gum accelerates colonic transit time and improves symptoms in adults with chronic constipation. *Dig Dis Sci.*, 2014; 59: 2207-2214, DOI: 10.1007/s10620-014-3135-1.
 40. Penagini, R., Velio, P., Vigorelli, R., Bozzani, A., Castagnone, D., Ranzi, T., and Branchi, P. A. (1986): The effect of dietary guar on serum cholesterol, intestinal transit, and fecal output in man. *Am. J Gastroenterol.*, 81: 123-125.

41. Finley JW, Soto-Vaca A, Heimbach J, et al. Safety Assessment and Caloric value of partially hydrolyzed guar gum. *Journal of Agricultural and food chemistry*, 2013; 61: 1756-1771, DOI: 10.1021/jf304910k.
42. Takahashi H, Yang SI, Hayashi CH, et al. Effect of partially hydrolyzed guar gum on fecal output in human volunteers. *Nutr Res.*, 1993; 13: 649-657, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0271-5317\(05\)80557-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0271-5317(05)80557-3).
43. Takahashi, H., Yang, S. I., Hayashi, C., Kim, M., Yamanaka, J., and Yamamoto, T. (1993): Effect of partially hydrolyzed guar gum on fecal output in human volunteers. *Nutr. Res.*, 13: 649-657.
44. Benninga MA, Voskuijl WP, Taminiou JA. Childhood constipation: is there new light in the tunnel? *J Pediatr Gastroenterol Nutr.*, 2004; 39: 448-64.
45. Evaluation and treatment of constipation in infants and children: recommendations of the North American Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition. Constipation Guideline Committee of the North American Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition. *J Pediatr Gastroenterol Nutr.*, 2006; 43: e1-13.
46. Alam NH, Meier R, Rausch T, et al. Effects of a partially hydrolyzed guar gum on intestinal absorption of carbohydrate, protein and fat: a double-blind controlled study in volunteers. *Clin Nutr.*, 1998; 17: 125-9.
47. Thompson WG, Longstreth GF, Drossman DA, Heaton KW, Irvine EJ, Muller-Lissner SA. Functional bowel disorders and functional abdominal pain. *Gut.*, 1999; 45(suppl 2): 43-7.
48. Vasant DH, Paine PA, Black CJ, et al. British Society of Gastroenterology guidelines on the management of irritable bowel syndrome. *Gut.*, 2021; 70: 7: 1214-1240. doi:10.1136/gutjnl-2021-324598.
49. Cash BD, Chey WD. Irritable bowel syndrome—an evidence-based approach to diagnosis. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther.*, 2004; 19: 1235-45.
50. Kopczyńska M, Mokros Ł, Pietras T, Małecka-Panas E. Quality of life and depression in patients with irritable bowel syndrome. *Prz Gastroenterol.*, 2018; 13(2): 102-108. doi:10.5114/pg.2018.75819.
51. Zhang T, Zhang C, Zhang J, Sun F, Duan L. Efficacy of probiotics for irritable bowel syndrome: a systematic review and network meta-analysis. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol.*, 2022; 12: 859967. doi: 10.3389/fcimb.2022.859967.

52. Cash BD, LacyBE, RaoT, Earnest DL. Rifaximin and eluxadoline— newly approved treatments for diarrhea-predominant irritable bowel syndrome: what is their role in clinical practice alongside alosetron? *Expert Opin Pharmacother*, 2016; 17(3): 311–322. doi: 10.1517/14656566.2016.1118052.
53. KwanAC, HuWH, ChanYK, YeungYW, LaiTS, YuenH. Prevalence of irritable bowel syndrome in Hong Kong. *J Gastroenterol Hepatol.*, 2002; 17(11): 1180–1186. doi:10.1046/j.1440-1746.2002.02871.x.
54. Maxion-Bergemann S, Thielecke F, Abel F, Bergemann R. Costs of irritable bowel syndrome in the UK and US. *Pharmacoeconomics.*, 2006; 24(1): 21–37. doi:10.2165/00019053-200624010-00002.
55. Longstreth GF, Thompson WG, Chey WD, Houghton LA, Mearin F, Spiller RC. Functional bowel disorders. *Gastroenterology*, 2006; 130(5): 1480–1491. doi:10.1053/j.gastro.2005.11.061.
56. FordAC, Moayyedi P, LacyBE, et al. American College of Gastroenterology monograph on the management of irritable bowel syndrome and chronic idiopathic constipation. *Am J Gastroenterol.*, 2014; 109(suppl 1): S2–S26; quiz S27. doi:10.1038/ajg.2014.187.
57. Allen P, Setya A, Lawrence VN. *Pediatric Functional Constipation*. Treasure Island, FL: StatPearls Publishing, 2022.
58. Savarino E, Zingone F, Barberio B, et al. Functional bowel disorders with diarrhoea: clinical guidelines of the United European Gastroenterology and European Society for Neurogastroenterology and Motility. *United Eur Gastroenterol J.*, 2022; 10(6): 556–584. doi: 10.1002/ueg2.12259.
59. El-Salhy M, Ystad SO, Mazzawi T, Gundersen D. Dietary fiber in irritable bowel syndrome (review). *Int J Mol Med.*, 2017; 40(3): 607–613. doi:10.3892/ijmm.2017.3072.
60. Axelrod CH, Saps M. The role of fiber in the treatment of functional gastrointestinal disorders in children. *Nutrients*, 2018; 10(11): 1650. doi:10.3390/nu10111650.
61. NivE, HalakA, TiomnyE, et al. Randomized clinical study: partially hydrolyzed guar gum (PHGG) versus placebo in the treatment of patients with irritable bowel syndrome. *Nutr Metab (Lond)*, 2016; 13: 10. doi:10.1186/s12986-016-0070-5.
62. Takahashi H, Wako N, Okubo T, Ishihara N, Yamanaka J, Yamamoto T. Influence of partially hydrolyzed guar gum on constipation in women. *J Nutr Sci Vitaminol (Tokyo)*, 1994; 40(3): 251–259. doi: 10.3177/jnsv.40.251.

63. Patrick PG, Gohman SM, Marx SC, DeLegge MH, Greenberg NA. Effect of supplements of partially hydrolyzed guar gum on the occurrence of constipation and use of laxative agents. *J Am Diet Assoc.*, 1998; 98(8): 912–914. doi:10.1016/s0002-8223(98)00210-7.
64. Rao TP, Quartarone G. Role of guar fiber in improving digestive health and function. *Nutrition*, 2019; 59: 158–169. doi:10.1016/j.nut.2018.07.109.
65. Chan TC, Yu VMW, Luk JKH, Chu LW, Yuen JKY, Chan FHW. Effectiveness of partially hydrolyzed guar gum in reducing constipation in long term care facility residents: a randomized single-blinded placebo-controlled trial. *J Nutr Health Aging*, 2022; 26(3): 247–251. doi:10.1007/s12603-022-1747-2.
66. Parkman HP, Yates K, Hasler WL, et al. Clinical features of idiopathic gastroparesis vary with sex, body mass, symptom onset, delay in gastric emptying, and gastroparesis severity. *Gastroenterology*, 2011; 140(1): 101–115. doi:10.1053/j.gastro.2010.10.015.
67. Zikos TA, Kamal AN, Neshatian L, et al. High prevalence of slow transit constipation in patients with gastroparesis. *J Neurogastroenterol Motil.* 2019; 25(2): 267–275.
68. Yamatoya K, Sekiya K, Yamada H. Effects of partially hydrolyzed guar gum on postprandial plasma glucose and lipids levels in humans. *J Jpn Soc Nutr Food Sci.*, 1993; 46: 199–203.
69. Lina BAR. Sub-chronic (13 week) oral toxicity study with Sun fiber and Sun fiber ST in rats. TNO report V97.080. Amsterdam: TNO Nutrition and Food Research Institute, 1997.
70. Takahashi H, Yang SI, Hayashi CH, Kim M, Yamanaka J, Yamamoto T. Effect of partially hydrolyzed guar gum on fecal output in human volunteers. *Nutr Res.*, 1993; 13: 649–57.
71. Yamatoya K, Kuwano K, Suzuki J, Mitamura T, Sekiya K. Effect of hydrolyzed guar gum on frequency and feeling of defecations in humans. *J Appl Glycosci.*, 1995; 42: 2517.
72. Spapen H, Diltoer M, Van Malderen C, Opdenacker G, Suys E, Huyghens L. Soluble fiber reduces the incidence of diarrhea in septic patients receiving total enteral nutrition: a prospective, double-blind, randomised, and controlled trial. *Clin Nutr.*, 2001; 20: 301–5.
73. Parisi GC, Zilli M, Miani MP, Carrara M, Bottona E, Verdianelli G, et al. High-fiber diet supplementation in patients with irritable bowel syndrome (IBS). A multicenter, randomized open trial comparison between wheat bran diet and partially hydrolyzed guar gum (PHGG). *Dig Dis Sci.*, 2002; 47: 1697–704.

74. Parisi G, Bottona E, Carrara M, Cardin F, Faedo A, Goldin D, et al. Treatment effects of partially hydrolyzed guar gum (PHGG) on symptoms and quality of life of patients with irritable bowel syndrome (IBS). A multicenter, randomized open trial. *Dig Dis Sci.*, 2005; 50: 1107–12.
75. Fennerty MB. Traditional therapies for the irritable bowel syndrome: an evidence-based appraisal. *Rev Gastroenterol Disord.*, 2003; 3(suppl 2): S18–24.
76. Mertz HR. Irritable bowel syndrome. *N Engl J Med.*, 2003; 349: 2136–46.
77. Connell AM: The effects of dietary fiber on gastrointestinal motor function. *Am J Clin Nutr.*, 1978; 31: S152–S156.
78. Francis CY, Whorwell PJ: Bran and irritable bowel syndrome: Time for reappraisal. *Lancet*, 1994; 344: 39–40.
79. Lewis MJ, Whorwell PJ: Bran: May irritate irritable bowel. *Nutrition*, 1998; 14: 470–471.
80. Haderstoffer B, Psycholgin D, Whitehead WE, Schuster MM: Intestinal gas production from bacterial fermentation of undigested carbohydrate in irritable bowel syndrome. *Am J Gastroenterol*, 1989; 84: 375–378.
81. Sperling MS, McQuaid KR: Rational medical therapy of functional GI disorders. In *Handbook of Functional Gastrointestinal Disorders*. KW Olden (ed). New York, Marcel Dekker, 1996; 269–328.
82. Klein KB. Controlled treatment trials in the irritable bowel syndrome: A critique. *Gastroenterology*, 1988; 95: 232–241.
83. Mangel AW, Hahn BA, Heath AT, Northcutt AR, Kong S, Dukes GE, McSorley D: Adequate relief as an endpoint in clinical trials in irritable bowel syndrome. *J Intern Med Res.*, 1998; 26:76–81.
84. Clouse RE, Mayer EA, Aziz Q, Drossman DA, Dumitrascu DL, Mönnikes H, Naliboff BD. Functional abdominal pain syndrome. *Gastroenterology*, 2006; 130: 1492-1497 [PMID: 16678562 DOI: 10.1053/j.gastro.2005.11.062.].
85. Apley J, Naish N. Recurrent abdominal pains: a field survey of 1,000 school children. *Arch Dis Child*, 1958; 33: 165-170 [PMID: 13534750 DOI: 10.1136/adc.33.168.165].
86. Walker LS, Lipani TA, Greene JW, Caines K, Stutts J, Polk DB, Caplan A, Rasquin-Weber A. Recurrent abdominal pain: symptom subtypes based on the Rome II Criteria for pediatric functional gastrointestinal disorders. *J Pediatr Gastroenterol Nutr.*, 2004; 38: 187-191 [PMID: 14734882 DOI: 10.1097/00005176-200402000-00016].

87. Son YJ, Jun EY, Park JH. Prevalence and risk factors of irritable bowel syndrome in Korean adolescent girls: a school based study. *Int J Nurs Stud.*, 2009; 46: 76-84 [PMID: 18722617 DOI: 10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2008.07.006].
88. Connell AM. The effects of dietary fiber on gastrointestinal motor function. *Am J Clin Nutr.*, 1978; 31: S152-S156 [PMID: 101074].
89. Heizer WD, Southern S, McGovern S. The role of diet in symptoms of irritable bowel syndrome in adults: a narrative review. *J Am Diet Assoc.*, 2009; 109: 1204-1214 [PMID: 19559137 DOI: 10.1016/j.jada.2009.04.012].
90. Feldman W, McGrath P, Hodgson C, Ritter H, Shipman RT. The use of dietary fiber in the management of simple, childhood, idiopathic, recurrent, abdominal pain. Results in a prospective, double-blind, randomized, controlled trial. *Am J Dis Child.*, 1985; 139: 1216-1218 [PMID: 2998181].
91. Johnson, C.M.etal.Meta-analyses of colorectalcancerriskfactors. *CancerCausesControl*, 2013; 24: 1207–1222.
92. VonRoon, A.C. etal. TheriskofcancerinpatientswithCrohn’s disease.*Dis.ColonRectum*, 2007; 50: 839–855.
93. Sung, H.etal.Global cancer statistics 2020:GLOBOCAN estimatesof Incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185countries. *CACancerJ.Clin.*71, 209–249(2021).
94. Amersi,F.,Agustin,M.&Ko,C.Y.Colorectalcancer:epidemiology,riskfactors,andhealthservices.*Clin.ColonRectalSurg*, 2005; 18: 133–140.
95. Chau, C.F. & Huang,Y.L.Effects of the insoluble fiber derived from *Passiflora edulis* seed plasma and he paticlipids and fecal out put. *Mol.Nutr.FoodRes.*, 2005; 49: 786–790.
96. Gill, S. K., Rossi, M., Bajka, B. & Whelan, K. Dietary fiber in gastrointestinal health and disease. *Nat. Rev. Gastroenterol. Hepatol.*, 2021; 18: 101–116.
97. Hunt,J.E.,Hartmann,B.,Schoonjans,K.,Holst,J.J.&Kissow,H. Dietary Fiber Is Essential to Maintain Intestinal Size, L-Cell Secretion, and Intestinal Integrity in Mice. *Front. Endocrinol.*, 2021; 12: 640602.
98. Macia, L. et al. Metabolite-sensing receptors GPR43 and GPR109A facilitate dietary fibre-induced gut homeostasis through regulation of the inflammasome. *Nat. Commun*, 2015; 6: 6734.
99. Abe, A. et al. Partially hydrolyzed guar gum is associated with improvement in gut health, sleep, and motivation among healthy subjects. *J. Clin. Biochem. Nutr.*, 2023; 72: 189–197.

100. Hiel, S. et al. Effects of a diet based on inulin-rich vegetables on gut health and nutritional behavior in healthy humans. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.*, 2019; 109: 1683–1695.
101. Valcheva, R. et al. Inulin-type fructans improve active ulcerative colitis associated with microbiota changes and increased short chain fatty acids levels. *Gut Microbes.*, 2019; 10: 334–357.
102. Bretin, A. et al. Psyllium fiber protects against colitis via activation of bile acid sensor farnesoid X receptor. *Cell Mol. Gastroenterol. Hepatol.*, 2023; 15: 1421–1442.
103. Yoon, S. J., Chu, D. C. & Raj Juneja, L. Chemical and physical properties, safety and application of partially hydrolyzed guar gum as dietary fiber. *J. Clin. Biochem Nutr.*, 2028; 42: 1–7.
104. Parang, B., Barrett, C. W. & Williams, C. S. AOM/DSS model of colitis-associated cancer. *Methods Mol. Biol.*, 2019; 1422: 297–307.
105. Alberti KG, Eckel RH, Grundy SM, et al. (2009) Harmonizing the metabolic syndrome: a joint interim statement of the International Diabetes Federation Task Force on Epidemiology and Prevention; National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute; American Heart Association; World Heart Federation; International Atherosclerosis Society; and International Association for the Study of Obesity. *Circulation*, 120: 1640–1645.
106. Mottillo S, Filion KB, Genest J, et al. (2010) The metabolic syndrome and cardiovascular risk: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Am Coll Cardiol.*, 56: 1113–1132.
107. Ley SH, Harris SB, Mamakeesick M, et al. (2009) Metabolic syndrome and its components as predictors of incident type 2 diabetes mellitus in an Aboriginal community. *CMAJ.*, 180: 617–624.
108. Papathanasopoulos A & Camilleri M (2009) Dietary fiber supplements: effects in obesity and metabolic syndrome and relationship to gastrointestinal functions. *Gastroenterology*, 138: 6572.
109. Silva FM, Steemburgo T, de Mello V, et al. (2011) High dietary glycemic index and low fiber content are associated with metabolic syndrome in patients with type 2 diabetes. *J Am Coll Nutr.*, 30: 141–148.
110. Yoon SJ, Chu DC & Raj Juneja L (2008) Chemical and physical properties, safety and application of partially hydrolyzed guar gum as dietary fiber. *J Clin Biochem Nutr.*, 42: 1–7.
111. Slavin JL & Greenberg N (2003) Partially hydrolyzed guar gum: clinical nutrition uses. *Nutrition*, 19: 549–552.

112. Kirsten R, Domning B, Nelson K, et al. Influence of guar on serum lipids in patients with hyperlipidemia. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol.*, 1989; 37: 117-20.
113. Miettinen TA, Tarpila S. Serum lipids and cholesterol metabolism during guar gum, plantago ovata and high fibre diets. *Clin Chim Acta.*, 1989; 183: 253-62.
114. Todd PA, Benfield P, Goa KL. Guar gum. A review of its pharmacological properties. And use as a dietary adjunct in hypercholesterolemia. *Drugs*, 1990; 39: 917-28.
115. Behall KM. Effect of soluble fibers on plasma lipids, glucose tolerance and mineral balance. *Adv Exp Med Biol.*, 1990; 270: 7-16.
116. Jenkins DIA. Dietary fiber. Diabetes, and hyperlipidemia. *Lancet*, 1979; 2: 1287-90.
117. Aro A, Uusitupa M, Voutilainen E, Hersio K, Korhonen T, Siitonen O. Improved diabetic control and hypocholesterolaemic effect induced by long-term dietary supplementation with guar gum in type 2 (insulin-independent) diabetes. *Diabetologia*, 1981; 2 1: 29-33.
118. Smith U, Holm G. Effect of modified guar gum preparations on glucose and lipid levels in diabetics and healthy volunteers. *Atherosclerosis.*, 1982; 45: 1-10.
119. Steemburgo T, Dall'Alba V, Almeida JC, et al. (2009) Intake of soluble fibers has a protective role for the presence of metabolic syndrome in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Eur J Clin Nutr.*, 63: 127–133.
120. Gin H, Orgerie MB, Aubertin I. The influence of guar gum on absorption of metformin from the gut in healthy volunteers. *Horm Metab Res.*, 1989; 21: 81-3.
121. Uusitupa M, Sodervik H, Silvasti M, Karttunen P. Effects of a gel forming dietary fiber, guar gum. On the absorption of glibenclamide and metabolic control and serum lipids in patients with non-insulin dependent (type 2) diabetes. *Int J Clin Pharmacol Ther Toxicol.*, 1990; 28: 153-7.
122. Ebeling P, Yki-Jarvinen H, Aro A, Helve E, Sinisalo M, Koivisto VA. Glucose and lipid metabolism and insulin sensitivity in type 1 diabetes: the effect of guar gum. *Am J Clin Nutr.*, 1988; 48: 98-103.
123. Bruttomesso D, Briani G, Bilardo G, et al. The medium-term effect of natural or extractive dietary fibres on plasma amino acids and lipids in type I diabetics. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.*, 1989; 6: 149-55.
124. Vaaler S, Hanssen KF, Dahl-Jorgensen K, et al. Diabetic control is improved by guar gum and wheat bran supplementation. *Diabetic Med.*, 1986; 3: 230-3.
125. Pyorala K, Laakso M, Uusitupa M. Diabetes and atherosclerosis: an epidemiologic view. *Diabetes Metab Rev.*, 1987; 3: 463-524.

126. Niemi MK, Keina`nen-Kiukaanniemi SM & Salmela PI (1988) Long-term effects of guar gum and microcrystalline cellulose on glycaemic control and serum lipids in type 2 diabetes. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol.*, 34: 427–429.
127. Uusitupa M, Siitonen O, Savolainen K, et al. (1989) Metabolic and nutritional effects of long-term use of guar gum in the treatment of noninsulin-dependent diabetes of poor metabolic control. *Am J Clin Nutr.*, 49: 345–351.
128. Stahl M & Berger W (1990) Compared effect of guar gum, wheat bran and placebo on carbohydrate and lipid metabolism in type II diabetic. *Schweiz Med Wochenschr*, 120: 402–408.
129. Chuang LM, Jou TS, Yang WS, et al. (1992) Therapeutic effect of guar gum in patients with non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. *J Formos Med Assoc.*, 91: 15–19.
130. Palem, R. R., Rao, K. M., & Kang, T. J. (2019). Self healable and dual-functional guar gum-grafted polyacrylamidoglycolic acid-based hydrogels with nano-silver dressings. *Carbohydrate for wound polymers*, 223: 115074. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2019.115074.
131. Jhundoo, H. D., Siefen, T., Liang, A., Schmidt, C., Lokhnauth, J., Moulari, B., ... & Lamprecht, A. (2021). Anti-inflammatory effects of acacia and guar gum in 5-amino salicylic acid formulations in experimental colitis. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*: X, 3, 100080. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpx.2021.100080.